

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Study of variability, correlation and heritability of physiological and yield related traits in Bambara groundnut [*Vigna subterranea* (L.) Verdc.] in Burkina Faso

Diane Judicaelle KAMBOU ^{1,*}, Hervé NANDKANGRE ², Moussa N'golo KONATE ³, Adjima OUOBA ⁴, Mahama OUEDRAOGO ⁵ and Mahamadou SAWADOGO ¹

¹ Training and Research Unit – Life and Earth Sciences University Joseph KI-ZERBO, 03 BP 7021 Ouagadougou 03, Burkina Faso.

² Tenkodogo University Center, Thomas SANKARA University, 12 BP 417 Ouagadougou 12, Burkina Faso.

³ Department of Life and Earth Sciences, Norbert ZONGO University, 01 BP 376 Koudougou 01, Burkina Faso.

⁴ Ziniaré University Center, Joseph KI-ZERBO University, 03 BP 7021 Ouagadougou 03, Burkina Faso.

⁵ Plant Production Department, Institute of Environment and Agricultural Research (INERA), 04 BP 8645 Ouagadougou, Burkina Faso.

GSC Advanced Research and Reviews, 2023, 16(02), 001–009

Publication history: Received on 16 June 2023; revised on 26 July 2023; accepted on 29 July 2023

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/gscarr.2023.16.2.0328>

Abstract

Bambara Groundnut [*Vigna subterranea* (L.) Verdcourt] is one of the most consumed leguminous crops in Burkina Faso. Through its food and nutritional qualities, it is undeniably to be taken into account for the attack on the food and nutritional security of populations. This work aims to contribute to a better knowledge of correlations between parameters, their mode of heritability and genetic progress. Sixteen quantitative traits were used to evaluate ninety Bambara Groundnut genotypes from three agro-climatic zones. These genotypes were sown during 2018 campaign in Rollo (north-central region of Burkina Faso) following a Fisher block design with four repetitions. The analysis of variance showed that means of parameters were highly significant ($P < 0.01$) except for plant height implying existence of an important variation between genotypes for these parameters. Phenotypic coefficients of variation varied from 5.96% to 121% and genotypic ones from 3.26% to 175%. Generally, phenotypic coefficients of variation (PCV) generated more than genotypic coefficients (GCV). However, the small differences between the values of these data mean showed the weak influence of environment on gene expression. Heritability recorded values $\geq 20\%$ and genetic advance varied from 57.96 to 2538.85. The parameters having recorded strong heritability's (20.35% to 97.95%) could be used in breeding and improvement programs of Bambara Groundnut by taking into account existing relations between these parameters. Programs to improve yield of Bambara Groundnut can only be envisaged after a good knowledge of the different relationships existing between yield parameters and their heritability.

Keywords: Variation; Yields; Heritability; Bambara groundnut; Burkina Faso

1. Introduction

Bambara groundnut [*Vigna subterranea* (L.) Verdcourt] is an important legume crop in Burkina Faso and Sub-saharan Africa [1, 2, 3]. It contributes to the food security of the poorest populations of the planet [4]. It is much appreciated in the human diet and is full of enormous nutritional qualities (39% to 62.12% carbohydrates, 19.41% to 21.64% proteins, 6.43% to 7.35% lipids, 6.84 % to 8.38% fiber, 10.71 mg to 13.15 mg calcium, 1.39 mg to 2.60 mg iron, 2.26 mg to 2.73 mg zinc in 100 g of seeds) [5]. It also has proven agronomic potentialities thanks to its ability to trap atmospheric nitrogen. [6] have reported a fixation capacity of 100 kg N ha⁻¹.

* Corresponding author: Diane Judicaelle KAMBOU

For several years in Burkina Faso, research works on Bambara groundnut are focused on several aspects such as identification of main fungal and viral diseases [7, 8, 9], conservation of Bambara groundnut seed [10], development of cultural options, in particular mounding periods [11] and mineral fertilizers utilisation [12] for enhancing and promote this culture. We can also report few works on genetic diversity assessment of cultivated accessions dealing with morphological and DNA markers (RAPD and SSR) [1, 13, 14, 15, 16] in order to deepen knowledge of this crop and highlight the diversity, which was hitherto not well known.

Despite its hardiness, forecasts in terms of Bambara groundnut yield remain difficult. The insufficiency and poor distribution of rainfalls, the decline in soil fertility are among other things, the major causes of the drop in yields. Setting up a breeding program based on varietal improvement in terms of productivity for yield and yield-related parameters of Bambara groundnut can be achieved through identification of traits showing high estimates of heritability and genetic advance [17]. In Burkina Faso, few studies have been focused on the relationship between yields related traits on Bambara groundnut accessions [18]. It is then necessary to deepen studies on different relationships between the parameters of yield and their heritability because information on phenotypic and genotypic relationships of physiological and yield related traits for yield in Bambara groundnut would be very useful to the breeders in developing an appropriate breeding strategy. The present work aims to study the variations of the parameters of the yield and to evaluate the heritability of these parameters in Bambara groundnut. The results of this research will make it possible to design effective programs to improve the yield of Bambara groundnut through releasing elite varieties with interesting agronomic characteristics.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Plant material and experimental site

Field evaluation was carried out on July 2018 in Rollo located in the North Central Region of Burkina Faso. Ninety Bambara groundnut genotypes used in this study were sourced from the Institute for the Environment and Agricultural Research (INERA) gene bank, Burkina Faso. Genotypes used were collected over different periods from the different phytogeographical zones. Six genotypes under selection by INERA, 18 genotypes collected from the Sahelian zone, 48 from Sudan-sahelian zone and 17 from Sudanian zone (Table 1).

Table 1 Genotypes studied and their origin

Origin	Genotypes
INERA	KVS 235, KVS 235 100 GY, KVS 246-1, KVS 246-2, KVS 246-3, Life 16-141
Sahelian	E 105b, E 108, E 110a, E 110b, E 111a, E 114, E 117, E 118, E 119, E 12, E 124a, E 124b, E 124c, E 125, E 126, E 13, E 59, E 61a
Sudan-sahelian	E 01, E 03, E 04, E 09, E 103a, E 103b, E 105a, E 107, E 111b, E 131, E 132, E 16a, E 48, E 49, E 51, E 53, E 56a, E 56b, E 56c, E 58, E 61b, E 62a, E 62b, E 62c, E 65, E 70b, E 71, E 72, E 75, Nob-Loc, E 76a, E 76b, E 78a, E 83a, E 83b, E 88b, E 89a, E 89b, E90, E 92, E 93b, E 94, E 95a, E 95b, E 97, E 98, ED8, KAYA 2014
Sudanian	E 101b, E 123, E 130, E 16b, E 20, E 22, E 23, E 25, E 26, E 27, E 28, E 44, E 76c, E 78b, E 83c, E 86, E 88a

2.2. Experimental design and agronomic practices

The experimental design used was a Completely Randomized Blocks device with four replications. Each Bambara groundnut genotypes was sowed on 4 m long as elementary plots. Seeds were sown on 4 m apart elementary plots with spacing of 40 cm between plot and 20 cm between the holes on the same plot. Twenty-one seeds were sowed in each plot. The replications were separated by 1 m. Recommended rate of 75 kg.ha⁻¹ of NPK (14-23-14) fertilizer was applied as a broadcast fertilizer at basal. Mounding was carried out 7 weeks after sowing. Regular weeding was made as need.

2.3. Data collection and analysis

Sixteen quantitative traits were observed during different stage of development and after harvest in accordance with Bambara groundnut descriptor established by the International Plant Genetic Resources Institute [19] (Table 2). Data collected were subjected to Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) in order to estimate the difference between studied traits among Bambara groundnut genotypes. The software IBM SPSS Statistics 20 software was used for analysis, and the significance was determined using F-test at 95% confidence.

Table 2 Method of scoring and code of quantitative parameter studied

Quantitative Parameters studied	Code	Method of scoring
Emergence date (day)	EMG	Estimate using calendar
Emergence at twenty-one days after sowing (number)	ETO	Counted
Days to first flowering (day)	FFL	Estimate using calendar
Days to 50% flowering (day)	HFL	Estimate using calendar
Number of leaves per plant (number)	NLP	Counted
Plant height (cm)	PHT	Measured
Diameter of the plant (cm)	DPL	Measured
Pod weight (g)	PWE	Measured
Number of pods per plant (number)	NPP	Counted
Number of pods with one seed (number)	N1S	Counted
Number of pod with two seeds (number)	N2S	Counted
Weight of seeds per plant(g)	WSP	Measured
Seed length (mm)	SDL	Measured
Seed width (mm)	SDW	Measured
Weight of 100 seeds (g)	WHS	Measured
Yield per square meter (g.m ²)	YIE	Measured

Genotypic and phenotypic correlations were performed using the formula of [20]:

$$r_{x,y} = \frac{COV(x,y)}{\sqrt{(\delta^2x)(\delta^2y)}}$$

Where $r_{x,y}$ is either genotypic or phenotypic correlation between variables x and y. $COV(x,y)$ is the genotypic or phenotypic covariance between two variables, δ^2x is the genotypic or phenotypic variance of the variable x, δ^2y is the genotypic or phenotypic variance of the yield y. The mean squares of the genotype and error for each character were used to calculate the genotypic variance (δ^2g), phenotypic variance (δ^2ph), Heritability (Broad sens) (H^2), Genotypic Coefficient of Variability (GCV), Phenotypic Coefficient of Variability (PCV) and Genetic Advance (GA) (Table 3) according to [21].

Table 3 Genetic parameters estimation

Parameter	Formula	Significance of terms
Genotypic variance (δ^2g)	$\delta^2g = (MSG - MSE)/r$	MSG: Mean Square of Genotype
Phenotypic variance (δ^2ph)	$\delta^2ph = \delta^2g + (MSE/r) = MSG/r$	MSE: Mean Square of error r: Number of replications
Heritability (Broad sense) (H^2)	$H^2 (\%) = (\delta^2g / \delta^2ph) * 100$	δg : Genotypic standard deviations δph : Phenotypic standard deviations
Genotypic Coefficient of Variability (GCV)	$GCV (\%) = (\delta g / X) * 100$	X: Mean of the character
Phenotypic Coefficient of Variability (PCV)	$PCV (\%) = (\delta ph / X) * 100$	
Genetic Advance (GA)	$GA = H^2 * \delta ph * K$	K = 2,06 (Selection coefficient)

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Genetic variability of Bambara groundnut

Mean squares and genetic parameters estimated of 90 Bambara groundnut genotypes are given in table 4. Analysis of results showed that all the characters are discriminant ($P < 0.05$) except plant height. This diversity implies not only a heterogeneity within genotypes, their diverse origins, but can also be attributed to the interaction genotypes-environment. [1, 16] had reported similar results on respectively 310 and 20 Bambara groundnut accessions in Burkina Faso. This studied population, with a broad genetic base could offer possibilities for improving Bambara groundnut through classic selection method.

The phenotypic coefficients variation (PCV) are higher than the genotypic coefficients variation (GCV) for all 16 traits studied. This would mean that genotype was influenced by environment in the phenotype expression. [22] classified values of GCV and PCV. Values greater than 20% indicated high variation, between 10 to 20% are moderated and less than 10% showed low variation. Low GCVs were recorded for plant height at maturity (3.26%), seed width (4.89%), days to 50% flowering (5.43%), seed length (5.54%), the first flowering (6.10%), emergence date (7.39%) and the diameter of the plant (9.67%). In contrast, higher values were recorded for yield (175.00%) and the number of pods containing a seed (121.00 %). Lower PCVs were recorded for seed dimensions (SDW = 5.96%, SDL = 6.62%) and flowering (FFL = 7.46%, HFL = 7.68%) and higher values with yield (261%), pods weight (121%) and number of pods (105%). High genotypic and phenotypic coefficient of variation indicates the presence of considerable amount of genetic variability for these characters in the material studied. [23] and [24] reached to the same findings respectively on *Arachis hypogea* and 33 lines of *Vigna subterranea* obtained from the germplasm collection of the International Institute of Tropical Agriculture, Ibadan in Nigeria. Our findings related to the results of [25] who worked on 12 Bambara groundnut cultivars from Nigeria. The relatively small difference observed between PCV and GCV may be due to the little influence of environment on character expression as found earlier [26, 27].

Heritability in broad sense is very important to predict the dependability of phenotypic traits. In fact, according to [28], heritability estimates are useful for quantitative selection because they provide information on the extent to which a particular trait can be inherited through generations. Following to the classification of [29], very high values were recorded for traits such as number of pods containing one seed (97.95%), weight of 100 seeds (91.54%) and emergence on the 21st day after sowing (81.67%) and moderate values for number of leaves per plant (55.75%), number of pods per plant (55.30%), days to 50% flowering (50.04%), pod weight (48.62%), yield (45.20%), and plant height (20.35%). High values of heritability in broad sense indicate the possibility of high genetic gain from selection for these characters [30]. These results are closed to [31] on *Vigna unguiculata* accessions. According to [32], a heritability of 100% implies that the phenotype could provide a perfect measure of the value of genotypes; therefore, these traits are very informative for desired traits. However, the breeding material could affect heritability, the traits taken into account and the environmental conditions of the study [33].

High genetic advance values were recorded for weight of 100 seeds (2538.85), number of leaves per plant (983.06), yield (876.43), number of pods with one seed (647.25) and diameter of plant (517.60). According to [29], high heritability combined with high genetic advance is indicative of additive gene action. High heritability coupled with low genetic advance would be the result of non-dependence genetic effects while low heritability coupled with low genetic

gain suggests that phenotypic selection may not be effective in improving these traits [27]. Moreover, selection based on both high values of heritability in broad sense and genetic advance would be more reliable in the expression of traits in offspring [34, 35].

Table 4 Mean squares, variance components heritability and genetic advance of 90 Bambara groundnut genotypes from Burkina Faso

Parameter	Mean	Mean Square	PCV (%)	GCV (%)	H ² (%)	GA
EMG	5.47	0.97**	9.00	7.39	67.39	68.33
ETO	16.17	19.19**	13.56	12.25	81.67	368.78
FFL	27.80	17.04**	7.46	6.10	66.96	285.97
HFL	31.87	23.72**	7.68	5.43	50.04	252.19
PHT	19.11	7.42ns	7.23	3.26	20.35	57.96
DPL	30.16	45.53**	11.22	9.67	74.23	517.60
NLP	54.14	291.70**	15.81	11.81	55.75	983.06
PWE	13.12	76.32**	121.00	84.00	48.62	212.95
NPP	17.91	65.10**	105.00	78.00	55.30	262.12
N1S	15.71	76.57*	111.00	110.00	97.95	647.25
N2S	0.56	0.93**	78.00	64.00	67.65	124.18
WSP	9.02	37.14**	68.00	56.00	70.71	419.16
WHS	57.62	645.68**	23.37	22.36	91.54	2538.85
SDL	11.16	1.96**	6.62	5.54	70.01	106.55
SDW	9.26	1.09**	5.96	4.89	67.29	76.48
YIE	59.32	1607.40**	261.00	175.00	45.20	876.43

Legend : EMG: Emergence date, ETO: Emergence at twenty-one days after sowing, FFL: Days to first flowering, HFL: Days to 50% flowering, PHT: Plant height, DPL: Diameter of the plant, NLP: Number of leaves per plant, PWE: Pod weigh, NPP: Number of pods per plant, N1S: Number of pods with one seed, N2S: Number of pod with two seeds, WSP: Weight of seeds per plant, WHS: Weight of 100 seeds, PWE: Pod weigh, SDL: Seed length, SDW: Seed width, YIE: Yield per square meter, ns: not significant, *: Indicate significant difference at 5%, ** indicate significant difference at 1%.
PCV: Phenotypic coefficient variation, GCV: Genotypic coefficient variation, H₂: Heritability in broad sense, GA: Genetic advance

3.2. Phenotypic and genotypic correlations among physiological and yield related traits

Phenotypic and genotypic correlations between the different characters are indicated in the table 5. The results showed negative and positive values for both genotypic and phenotypic correlations. In general, genotypic correlations were higher than their related phenotypic correlations for respective characters. This show a strong association between the characters taken in pair. This means that the environment has weak influence on the expression of traits and selection could be based on phenotypic traits. Significant and very significant positive correlations were recorded between weight of 100 seeds and emergence date ($r_p = 0.662$; $r_g = 0.965$), days to 50% flowering ($r_g = 0.500$), diameter of the plant ($r_p = 1.453$; $r_g = 2.021$), number of leaves per plant ($r_p = 1.604$; $r_g = 2.575$), seed length ($r_p = 3.1682$; $r_g = 4.637$) and seed width ($r_p = 3.850$; $r_g = 5.567$). Weight of seed per plant exhibited positive and significant correlations with number of leaves per plant ($r_p = 0.367$; $r_g = 0.289$), seed length ($r_p = 0.428$; $r_g = 0.618$) and seed width ($r_p = 0.646$; $r_g = 0.962$). Selection based on one or more of these parameters leads to improved yield performance. Some authors such as [36] and [26] have reached the same results. Correlation gives magnitude of association of different component traits. According to [37], the significant positive correlation among the yield-related traits suggest that these characters also make positive indirect contribution to the final grain.

Negative and strong genotypic correlations were observed between days to 50% flowering and yield parameters such as number of pods ($r_p = -0.385$; $r_g = -0.655$), number of pods with one seed ($r_p = -0.356$; $r_g = -0.606$), weight of seed per plant ($r_g = -0.314$) and weight of 100 seeds ($r_g = -0.500$). Reducing flowering time positively influences the yield parameters such as the number of pods number of pods with one seed, weight of pods, weight of seeds per plant and weight of 100 seeds. These correlations are particularly interesting in view of the short rainy seasons observed in

Burkina Faso. Selection based on genotypes with a short semi-flowering cycle enables early pod formation. Pods formed in this way will have sufficient time to fill with seeds before the rains shorten. [18] worked on the agronomic performance of eight Bambara groundnut genotypes reached to the similar findings. Emergence date was also negatively and strongly correlated to emergence at 21st DAS ($r_p = -0.333$; $r_g = -0.486$), number of pods ($r_g = -0.429$) and number of pods with one seed ($r_g = -0.324$). The earlier the emergence of the seedlings, the lower the performance of the pods and seeds. That is to say that the plants with late emergence have recorded good performance and vice versa.

Table 5 Estimated phenotypic (P) and genotypic (G) correlation coefficients

Parameters		ETO	FFL	HFL	DPL	PHT	NLP	PWE	NPP	N1S	N2S	SDL	SDW	WSP	WHS
EMG	rp	-0.333	0.350	0.302	0.372	0.099	0.689	0.081	-0.295	-0.222	-0.056	0.024	0.037	-0.053	0.662
	rg	-0.486	0.517	0.441	0.542	0.145	1.004	0.118	-0.429	-0.324	-0.081	0.034	0.054	-0.078	0.965
ETO	rp		-0.122	-0.076	-0.001	-0.019	-0.363	0.068	0.203	0.162	0.034	-0.014	0.038	0.136	0.005
	rg		-0.162	-0.100	-0.001	-0.025	-0.480	0.091	0.268	0.215	0.045	-0.018	0.050	0.181	0.006
FFL	rp			0.060	0.044	0.009	0.094	-0.015	-0.051	-0.047	-0.004	0.002	-0.001	-0.021	0.005
	rg			0.893	0.653	0.134	1.412	-0.221	-0.768	-0.708	-0.055	0.033	-0.016	-0.313	0.077
HFL	rp				0.403	0.126	0.610	-0.178	-0.385	-0.356	-0.014	0.013	-0.007	-0.185	-0.294
	rg				0.686	0.215	1.037	-0.303	-0.655	-0.606	-0.024	0.023	-0.012	-0.314	-0.500
DPL	rp					0.319	1.804	0.630	0.037	0.088	-0.021	0.104	0.081	0.290	1.453
	rg					0.444	2.510	0.877	0.052	0.122	-0.029	0.145	0.113	0.403	2.021
PHT	rp						1.526	0.596	0.113	0.157	-0.018	0.109	0.076	0.295	1.361
	rg						4.352	1.700	0.322	0.447	-0.050	0.312	0.218	0.840	3.880
NLP	rp							0.662	0.206	0.249	-0.001	0.094	0.057	0.367	1.604
	rg							1.063	0.331	0.400	-0.001	0.151	0.092	0.589	2.575
PWE	rp								0.055	0.056	0.000	0.008	0.008	0.055	0.179
	rg								0.076	0.077	0.001	0.011	0.011	0.076	0.249
NPP	rp									0.070	0.003	0.000	0.001	0.040	0.030
	rg									0.104	0.004	0.000	0.001	0.060	0.044
N1S	rp										0.002	0.001	0.001	0.041	0.040
	rg										0.003	0.001	0.001	0.049	0.048
N2S	rp											-0.004	-0.002	0.010	-0.079
	rg											-0.008	-0.004	0.019	-0.146
SDL	rp												0.161	0.422	3.168
	rg												0.235	0.618	4.637
SDW	rp													0.646	3.850
	rg													0.967	5.767
WSP	rp														0.148
	rg														0.212

4. Conclusion

Research carried out to determine the level of variability, the different types of correlation between characters and heritability has shown that there is considerable phenotypic diversity among Bambara groundnut accessions from

Burkina Faso. The significant correlations observed between studies at the level of genotypes and phenotypes offer possibilities of varietal selection because environment do not influence significantly the expression of the characters, mainly those related to yield. In order to improve the productivity of Bambara groundnut, it would be necessary to rely on the significant and positive correlations between the components of the yield and yield because for a good yield improvement program, the mode of inheritance of yield components must be understood. In addition, traits with high heritability coupled with high genetic advance values must be taken into consideration in a varietal improvement program.

Compliance with ethical standards

Acknowledgments

The authors are grateful to the McKnight foundation for the financial support in this work.

Disclosure of conflict of interest

This work was carried out in collaboration between all the authors. Author DJK collected the data, did the literature search and wrote the manuscript. The author HN carried out the statistical analyses and the correction of the manuscript. The author MNK participated in the set-up of the study and the data collection. Author AO wrote the protocol. The author MO and MS supervised the study. All authors have read and approved the final manuscript.

References

- [1] Ouédraogo M, Ouedraogo TJ, Tignere JB, Balma D, Dabire BC And Konate G. Characterization and evaluation of accessions of Bambara groundnut. *Sci. Nat.* 2008; 5(2), pp. 191–197.
- [2] Hillocks RJ, Bennett C, Mponda OM. Bambara nut: a review of utilisation, market potential and crop improvement. *African Crop Sci J.* 2012; 20:1-16.
- [3] Toure Y, Koné M, Silué S, Kouadio YJ. Prospecting, collection and agro-morphological characterization of voandzou morphotypes (*Vigna subterranea* (L.) Verdc) from the savanna zone in Ivory Coast. *European scientific journal.* 2013; 9:308-325.
- [4] Mkandawire CH. Review of bambara groundnut (*Vigna subterranea*) production in Sub-Sahara Africa, 464-470. *Agricultural Journal (Medwell Journals), Malawi.* 2007; vol 2 no.4, 464-470.
- [5] Hama-Ba F, Siedogo M, Ouedraogo M, Dao A, Dicko HM, and B. Diawara. Consumption patterns and nutritional value of food legumes in Burkina Faso. *Afr. J. Food Agric. Nutr. Dev.* 2017; 17(4): 12871-12888.
- [6] Musa M, Massawe F, Mayes S, Alshareef I, Singh A. Nitrogen fixation and N-Balance studies on Bambara groundnut (*Vigna subterranea* L. Verdc.) Landraces grown on tropical acidic soils of Malaysia. *Commun Soil Sci Plant Anal.* 2016; 47(4):533-542.
- [7] Ouoba A, Zida EP, Soalla RW, Bangratz M, Essowè P, Konaté MN, Nandkangré H, Ouédraogo M and Sawadogo M. Molecular characterization of the main fungi associated to Bambara groundnut foliar diseases in Burkina Faso. 2019; *Journal of Applied Biosciences* 133: 13574 – 13583.
- [8] Konate MN, Ouedraogo M, Neya BJ, Bangratz M, Palanga E, Nandkangre H, Ouoba A, Nanema R, Sawadogo N and Sawadogo M. Molecular characterization of virus isolates from genus Potyvirus infecting *Vigna subterranea* in Burkina Faso. *Afr. J. Biotechnol.* 2017; Vol. 16(39), pp. 1953-1961.
- [9] Ouili AS, Maiga Y, Nikiema M, Ilboudo I, Nikiema F, Ouoba A, Nandkangre H, Compaore COT, Kabre E, Ouedraogo M and Ouattara AS. Isolation of *Aspergillus flavus* strains from Bambara groundnut (*Vigna subterranea* (L.) Verdcourt) seeds and screening for the production of aflatoxin B1 and B2. 2022; *Int. J. Biol. Chem. Sci.* 16(6): 2470-2480.
- [10] Ouili AS, Maiga Y, Ouoba A, Nandkangre H, Compaore COT, Nikiema M, Ouedraogo M, Ouattara AS. Post-Harvest Management Practices of Bambara Groundnut (*Vigna subterranea* (L.) Verdc) Seeds in Burkina Faso. 2022; *European Scientific Journal, ESJ*, 18 (14), 239. <https://doi.org/10.19044/esj.2022.v18n14p239>.
- [11] Ouédraogo M, Zagré MB, Jorgensen ST and Liu F. Effect of mounding times on yield of bambara groundnut (*Vigna subterranea* (L.) Verdc.) landraces in Sahel-Burkina Faso. *African Journal of Agricultural Reseach.* 2012; 7(32), p.4505-4511.

- [12] Nandkangre H, Zongo KF, Kambou DJ, Bonkougou M, Konate NM, Ouoba A, Kima AS And Ouedraogo M. Effect of NPK application dates on agronomic parameters of two Bambara groundnut varieties cultivated on ferric Lixisol in northern Sudanian Sector of Burkina Faso. *World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews*. 2023; 19(01), 246–253.
- [13] Ouoba A, Zida SF, Ouédraogo M, Nandkangre H, Ouédraogo HM, Nanéma RK, Sawadogo N, Zida EP, Konaté MN, Congo AK, Soalla RW and Sawadogo M. Assessment of genetic diversity in Bambara groundnut (*Vigna subterranea* (L.) Verdcourt) landraces in Burkina Faso using microsatellite markers (SSR). *Agricultural Science Research Journal*. 2017 ; Vol. 7(3): 96 – 102.
- [14] Konate NM, Nandkangre H, Ouoba A, Zisa SF, Ouedraogo M, Sawadogo N, Nadembega S, Congo AK and Sawadogo M. Genetic diversity of bambara groundnut accessions from Burkina Faso using Random Amplified Polymorphic DNA markers. *International Journal of Current Research*. 2018; Vol. 10, Issue, 10, pp.74106-74111.
- [15] Kambou DJ, Nandkangre H, Ouoba A, Congo AK, Konate NM, Zida WMSF, Sawadogo N, Sawadogo M, Ouedraogo M. Molecular Characterization Using Microsatellites of Bambara Nut (*Vigna subterranea* [L.] Verdcourt) Landraces Cultivated in Burkina Faso. *Agricultural Sciences*. 2021 ; 12, 1119-1128.
- [16] Nandkangre H, Zongo KF, Kambou DJ, Ilboudo BY, Konate MN, Ouoba A, Kima AS, Ouedraogo HM, Traore ER and Ouedraogo M. Phenological, Morphological and Agronomic Characterization of Bambara Groundnut Genotypes on Plinthite Soil in East-centre Area, Burkina Faso. *Ann. Res. Rev. Biol*. 2022; vol. 37, no. 12, pp. 105-114.
- [17] Onwubiko NC, Uguru MI and Chimdi GO. Estimates of Genetic Parameters in Bambara Groundnut (*Vigna subterranea* (L.) VERDC.). *Plant Breed. Biotech*. 2019; 7(4):295~301
- [18] Nandkangre H, Kambou DJ, Ouoba A, Konate MN, Zongo FK, Traore ER, Kima AS, Nikiema B, Ilboudo YB and Ouedraogo M. Variability, correlations, genetic advance and heritability of physiological and agronomic parameters of Bambara groundnut (*Vigna subterranea* [L.] Verdc.) genotypes from Burkina Faso. *Int. J. Curr. Res. Biosci. Plant Biol*. 2022; 9(8): 9-16. doi: <https://doi.org/10.20546/ijcrbp.2022.908.002>.
- [19] IPGRI et Bamnet. 2000. Descriptors for Bambara groundnut (*Vigna subterranea* [L.] Verdc.) International Plant Genetic Resources Institute, Rome, Italy; International Institute of Tropical Agriculture, Ibadan, Nigeria, IPGRI/IITA/BAMNET, Rome.
- [20] Miller, P.A., J.C. Williams, H.F. Robinson and R.E. Comstock, 1958. Estimated of genotypic and environmental variances and covariance in upland cotton and their implication in selection. *Agronomy Journal*, 50: 126-131.
- [21] Jalata, Z., A. Ayana and H. Zeleke, 2011. Variability, heritability and genetic advance for some yield and yield related traits in Ethiopian barley (*Hordeum vulgare* L.) mandrake and crosses. *Internatinal. Journal of Plant Breeding and Genetics*, 5 (1):44-52.
- [22] Deshmukh SN, Basu MS, Reddy PS. Genetic variability, character associations and path coefficient of quantitative traits in Virginia bunch varieties of groundnut. *Indian J. Agric. Sci*. 1986; 56: 816-821.
- [23] Gonya NP, Venkataiah M, Revathi P and Srinivas B. Correlation and genetic variability studies in groundnut (*Arachis hypogaea* l.) genotypes. ISSN: 0975-2862 & E-ISSN: 2018; 0975-9158, Volume 10, Issue 2, pp.-354-356.
- [24] Onwubiko NC, Uguru MI and Chimdi GO. Estimates of Genetic Parameters in Bambara Groundnut (*Vigna subterranea* (L.) VERDC.). *Plant Breed. Biotech*. 2019; 7(4):295~301.
- [25] Jonah PM, Adeniji OT, & Wammanda, DT. Variability and genetic correlations for yield and yield characters in some Bambara groundnut (*Vigna subterranea*) cultivars. *Int. J. Agric. Biol*. 2010; 12, 303-307.
- [26] Khan MMH, Rafii MY, Ramlee SI, Jusoh M and Al Mamun. Genetic Variability, Heritability, and Clustering Pattern Exploration of Bambara Groundnut (*Vigna subterranea* L. Verdc) Accessions for the Perfection of Yield and Yield-Related Traits. *BioMed Research International*. 2020; Volume 2020, Article ID 2195797, 31 pages.
- [27] Donkor EF, Adjei RR, Amadu B, Boateng AS. Genetic variability, heritability and association among yield components and proximate composition of neglected and underutilized Bambara groundnut [*Vigna subterranea* (L.) Verdc] accessions for varietal development in Ghana. *Heliyon*. 2022; 8 e09691.
- [28] Bello OB, Ige SA, Azeez MA, Afolabi MS, Abdulmaliq SY, Mahamood J. Heritability and genetic advance for grain yield and its component characters in maize (*Zea mays* L.). *Int.J.Plant Res*. 2012; 2 (5), 138-145.
- [29] Johnson HW, Robinson HF and Comstock RE. Estimates of genetic and environmental variability in Soybeans. *Agronomy Journal*. 1955; 47 (7): 314-318.

- [30] Adebisi MA, Ariyo OJ, and Kehinde OB. Variation and correlation studies in quantitative characters in soybean. *The Ogun Journal of Agricultural Science*. 2004; vol. 3, no. 1, pp. 134–142.
- [31] Adeigbe OO, Adewale BD and Fawole IO. Genetic variability, stability and relationship among some Cowpea, *Vigna unguiculata* (L.) Walp breeding lines. *African Journal of Crop Science*. 2018; ISSN 2375-1231 Vol. 6 (7), pp. 001-006.
- [32] Allard RW. Principles of plant breeding, John Wiley and sons, New York. 1960.
- [33] Dabholkar AR. Elements of biometrical genetics. Concept Publishing Company, New Delhi, India. 1992; 431pp.
- [34] Shukla S, Bhargava AA, Chatterjee A, Srivastava A, Singh SP. Genotypic variability in vegetable amaranth (*Amaranthus tricolor* L.) for foliage yield and its contributing traits over successive cuttings and years. *Euphytica*. 2006; 151: 103-110.
- [35] Asfaw A, Ambachew D, Shah T, Blair MW. Trait associations in diversity panels of the two common bean (*Phaseolus vulgaris* L.) gene pools grown under well-watered and water-stress conditions. *Front. Plant Sci*. 2017; 8: 733.
- [36] Malek MA, Rafii MY, Afroz MSS, Nath UK and Mondal M. Morphological characterization and assessment of genetic variability, character association, and divergence in soybean mutants. *The Scientific World Journal*. 2014; vol. 2014, Article ID 968796, 12 pages.
- [37] Maunde SM, Tanimu B and Mahmud M. Correlation and path coefficient analysis of yield characters of bambara (*Vigna subterranea* L. Verdc.). *Afr. J. Environ. Sci. Technol. Vpl*. 2015; 9(1). pp. 12-15.